

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF WORKING WITH TEXTS IN DEVELOPING GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of the role of texts in developing grammatical competencies in future primary school teachers and in mastering the topics given in the subject program "Native Language - Reading Literacy and Methods of Teaching It".*

Keywords: *text linguistics, communicative function of the text, compositional structure, text creation skills.*

The role of texts in developing grammatical competencies in future primary school teachers and mastering the topics given in the subject program "Native Language - Reading Literacy and Methodology of Its Teaching" is significant.

As is known, sentences that are grammatically, stylistically and semantically connected for one purpose are considered texts. In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", the term "text" is explained as follows:

1. The term text (Arabic) is a shoulder, a written expression of speech - (text); 2. An author's work or document formed in writing or in print.

The above definitions do not fully reflect the content of the concept of "text". Text is considered the largest unit of speech and is the object of study of the syntax section in linguistics.

While conducting research on the problem of working with text in native language classes, scientist Kh.Gulomova approaches the issue as follows: "a text, in addition to expressing a complete and complete thought in comparison with a sentence, also encompasses broader and deeper information in the process of communicative communication. Since this feature is also inherent in proverbs and sayings, which are grammatically equivalent to sentences, they are considered small-scale texts. Therefore, it is appropriate to study and analyze linguistic phenomena not on the basis of individual words, word combinations or sentences, but on the basis of text."

It seems that the grammatical, stylistic and semantic connection of sentences for a specific purpose is the main characteristic of the text.

Issues related to text linguistics were initially observed by scientists of the Prague linguistic school, who analyzed this issue from a functional-semantic aspect. In 1974, a theoretical conference on text linguistics was held in Moscow, where several lectures and scientific information on this problem were heard. In the speeches of linguists, the complexity and multifacetedness of the problem of text linguistics were noted, as well as the fact that it is a new area in the science of linguistics.

Uzbek linguists have also conducted a number of scientific studies in the field of text linguistics. Researchers have studied issues such as the communicative function of the text, its compositional structure, and the structural-semantic and stylistic properties of its constituent parts.

The first views on the text can be found in the textbook “Modern Uzbek Literary Language”, published in collaboration with A.Gulomov and M.Askarova. The first textbook on the study of the text in Uzbek linguistics, entitled “Text Linguistics”, was published by A.Mamajonov. The textbook provides detailed theoretical information about the text for the first time in Uzbek linguistics. The International Scientific and Theoretical Conference on “Linguistic Interpretation of Special Texts and Activation of Communication Abroad” held in 1998 at the initiative of linguists of Samarkand State University testifies to the attention paid to the problems of textual studies in our linguistics. The conference was attended by philologists and scholars from Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, China, India, Switzerland, and Belarus, who exchanged views on current issues related to textual studies.

In the study of text linguistics in Uzbek linguistics, it is worth highlighting the textbook “Linguistic Analysis of a Literary Text”, created in collaboration with B.Orinbayev, R.Kungurov, and J.Lapasov. The textbook explains the general and specific linguistic features of the text, types of text, problems such as text composition and the use of language expression means in it using linguistic evidence.

In our opinion, a text is a meaningful and subordinate connection of words, word combinations, and sentences. When creating a text, the ability to choose words, correctly use grammatically related word combinations, and arrange sentences in an orderly manner are taken into account. It is required to avoid stylistic errors and shortcomings when creating a text.

The skill of creating a text is formed in the following way:

1. The student, first of all, learns the technique of creating a text, and is able to compose and write a text on his own.

2. In the process of working with a text dictionary, he understands what words should be used, and which word is appropriate in this case. He chooses the appropriate one from the given alternatives.

3. He learns to ask questions about the text. He isolates the main idea that is being said. He thinks independently in the process of answering questions, whether correctly or incorrectly.

4. In the process of choosing a title for some texts, he learns to understand the main idea in the text and reflect it in a short and meaningful sentence. In texts where a title is recommended, he determines and thinks about the extent to which this name is appropriate for the text.

5. In the process of working with the dictionary, the student learns the meaning of new words for himself, and his vocabulary increases. When studying texts, the main emphasis is on developing oral speech and thinking skills. However, there are also written assignments based on the text, which serve to improve written literacy. To improve the grammatical literacy of future primary school teachers, we can use historical, literary, scientific, related to other subjects, socio-political, even riddles and khanda texts.

AHMAD AL- FERGHANI

Ahmad al-Ferghani's full name is Abul Abbas Ahmad Ibn Muhammad Ibn Kathir al-Ferghani. He was born in the late 8th century in the city of Quba (now Quwa). The city of Quwa was one of the cultural and scientific centers of that time, and he lived in Quwa until the age of 20 and received his education there. His name spread widely from that time and he was invited to the city of Merv. Ahmad al-Farghani's name soon gained so much attention that at the age of 30-35 he was invited to the "House of Knowledge" in Baghdad, called the "City of Peace", that is, "Khizonat-al-hikma" or "Bayt-ul-hikmat". Most of his works were created while he was living in

the presence of Mamun. His famous book “Kitab Jawame’ ilm an nujum wal - harakat as-samoviya” (“Astronomy and the Movement of the Planets”) was also created during that period. The scientist’s works began to be taught in universities in Italy, France and Germany as early as the 12th century. During this period, his famous works were translated into Latin and into Hebrew by Ya’qub Anaduli.

Ahmad al-Ferghani became famous in Europe under the name Alfraganus. His manuscripts are spread all over the world. The existence of the scientist’s manuscripts has been registered in Princeton University in America, St. Petersburg, Cairo, Paris, Mexico City and India. Restoring the names and works of our great ancestors like al-Ferghani will be an instructive lesson in understanding our national values and perceiving our identity. (116 words)

Tasks:

1. Who else do you know of the early Renaissance encyclopedists? Why do we call them encyclopedists? Write down your opinion and justify it.
2. Identify the correct sentence. Fill in the boxes with the correct information. (√)

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3. Identify the incorrect statement. Tick the boxes with incorrect information. (X)

At the age of 35-40, he was invited to Baghdad, known as the "City of Peace", to the "House of Knowledge", that is, "Khizonat-al-hikma" or "Bayt-ul-hikmat".

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In conclusion, the exercises given in the lessons "Native Language - Reading Literacy and Methods of Teaching It" to develop the grammatical competencies of future primary school teachers serve to form the skills of expressing thoughts in written form: writing, creating creative texts, speaking, listening comprehension and reading, therefore, more than just exercises on the subject should be given. After all, the tasks and texts given in the textbook teach future primary school teachers to develop language sensitivity, thinking, practical mastery of the grammatical structure and methodology of the mother tongue, and ultimately create creative texts. Working with texts in practical lessons on the subject "Native Language - Reading Literacy and Methods of Teaching It" is important for future primary school teachers to develop their speech and grammatical competencies aimed at thinking, understanding the opinions of others, and expressing their thoughts competently both orally and in writing.

REFERENCES

1.O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati. 5-jild. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007. – 687 b

2.G‘ulomova X. Ona tili darslarida matn ustida ishlash // Til va adabiyot ta’limi. – Toshkent, 2020. – № 8. – B. 5-6b

3. Maxsus matnlarning lingvistik talqini (interpretatsiyasi) va chet ellarda muloqot qilishni faollashtirish” mavzuidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-nazariy konferensiya. – Samarqand, 1998. – 107 b

4. O‘rinboyev B., Qo‘ng‘urov R., Lapasov J. Badiiy tekstning lingvistik tahlili. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 1990. – 110 b.